

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PREVENTION OF PROGNATHISM FORMATION IN CHILDREN DURING PRIMARY AND MIXED DENTITION PERIODS

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One of the primary goals in modern dentistry is the prevention of dental and maxillofacial disorders, with a focus on identifying dental anomalies early based on initial symptoms and addressing root causes through preventive measures. This is especially relevant in pediatric dentistry. Causes of dental and maxillofacial anomalies vary, with primary factors including harmful habits such as thumb-sucking, lip-biting, and poor posture, as well as functional issues like mouth breathing, chewing and swallowing difficulties, and speech irregularities (Okushov V.R., 2004; Arsenina O.I., 2009). Tongue position also plays a significant role in prognathism formation (Persin L.S., 2003). The stability of prognathism treatment results greatly depends on correcting these functional issues, early detection, and intervention (Khoroshilkina F.Ya., 2006). Correcting occlusal issues during mixed dentition has become a key trend in global orthodontic practice, with emphasis on non-invasive therapy that addresses soft tissue influences to yield substantial results in early dentition stages (Gvozdeva Yu.M., 2010).

Objective: To identify early prognathism signs in children during primary and early mixed dentition and to develop preventive strategies for various prognathism types.

Materials and Methods: The study involved an examination of children in Bukhara. Children with maxillofacial pathology were categorized into three groups according to WHO recommendations: Group 1 (67%) with combined anomalies, Group 2 (25%) with dental anomalies, and Group 3 (16%) with dental arch and occlusal anomalies. Each group received a customized prevention and treatment plan. The study identified a prevalence of maxillofacial anomalies at 64%, with combined anomalies in 67%, dental anomalies in 25%, and dental arch and occlusal anomalies in 16%. Key risk factors included frequent illnesses during the first year (95%), soft tissue anomalies (78%), hereditary predisposition (63%), and maternal chronic illnesses (52%).

Preventive programs for pregnant women included dental education through individual counseling, brochures, videos, and practical hygiene training. Pre-

ventive measures started at six months of age with bi-annual follow-ups, emphasizing parental responsibility for their children's dental health.

To prevent maxillofacial anomalies, parents were advised to use a short, resilient pacifier with small holes, promoting a 15-20 minute feeding duration. Such pacifiers encourage jaw movement, helping advance the mandible during sucking and strengthening its position relative to the maxilla. Careful bottle positioning to avoid mandibular pressure is also crucial to prevent malocclusion development.

If feeding duration decreases, children may develop habits like thumb-sucking. In this case, a pacifier should be given for 5-10 minutes. After primary teeth eruption, pacifier use should be gradually discontinued for preventive purposes.

By focusing on early orthodontic prevention, acquired occlusal anomalies can often be avoided. When misalignment becomes apparent in the primary dentition, a range of measures can address the underlying causes and guide the positioning of emerging permanent teeth. These interventions harness the body's self-regulation mechanisms by eliminating harmful myofunctional habits. Preventive efforts to reduce prognathism development in children showed a 75% reduction in malocclusion cases. The prevention program developed for various occlusal disorders in children during primary and mixed dentition stages enables early correction of emerging prognathism.

References:

1. Abduazimov, A.D., Nazarova, V.F., Shomukhamedova, F.A., et al. Evaluation of Treatment Methods for Patients with Anomalies in the Position of Individual Teeth // *Stomatologiya*. – 2002. – No. 1-2. – P. 59-61.
2. Alimsky, A.V. Mechanism of Eruption of Permanent Teeth and Causes of Maxillofacial System Anomalies // *Stomatology*. – 2000. – No. 3. – P. 51-52.
3. Biryukova, O.P. Influence of Functional State of Maxillofacial Muscles and Posture on the Formation of Distal Occlusion in Children Aged 6-12: Dissertation. ... Candidate of Medical Sciences. – Moscow, 2005. – 124 p.

4. Volodatsky, V.M. Clinical and Comprehensive Treatment of Combined Forms of Dental Occlusion Anomalies in Children and Adolescents: Dissertation Abstract. ... Doctor of Medical Sciences. – Stavropol, 2010. – 42 p.

5. Gvozdeva, Yu.V. Dysfunction of Soft Tissues in the Maxillofacial Area in Children: Mechanisms Affecting the Formation of the Maxillofacial System and Opportunities for Early Correction Using Myofunctional Appliances: Dissertation Abstract. ... Doctor of Medical Sciences. – Perm, 2010. – 44 p.

6. Nazarova, V.F., Muslimova, D.M. Analysis of Primary Orthodontic Patients' Examination Results

Who Visited the Orthodontic Clinic at the First Tashkent State Medical Institute // Stomatology. – 2005. – No. 3/4. – P. 167-169.

7. Persin, L.S., et al. A New Method for Assessing Segment Sizes of Dental Arches and Diagnosing Their Occlusion // Stomatology. – 2003. – No. 4. – P. 64-67.

8. Khoroshilkina, F.Ya. Orthodontics, Dental Defects, Dental Arch Anomalies, Occlusal Anomalies, Morphofunctional Disorders in the Maxillofacial Region and Their Comprehensive Treatment. – Moscow: Medical Information Agency, 2006. – 544 p.